

Level of Job Satisfaction of Temporary Agriculture Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Homa-Bay County, Kenya

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Abstract: A satisfied employee is more motivated and shows commitment to duty. In Kenya, labour turnover in public secondary schools among agriculture teachers has been common. This situation could be related to lack of job satisfaction among these teachers. Teacher shortage in Homa-Bay County had precipitated hiring of Temporary Agriculture Teachers to alleviate the shortage however, there was little that was known about their levels of job satisfaction. This study therefore sought to analyse the job satisfaction levels of temporary agriculture teachers in public secondary schools in Homa-Bay County, Kenya. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The target population was 316 agriculture teachers employed by the Board of Management (BOM) who were in service during the study period. Proportionate stratified random sampling was used to select 176 teachers. A validated questionnaire with closed ended items was used to collect data. Data collection was preceded by a pilot test with 29 temporary agriculture teachers from Migori County, whose analysis resulted in a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics on SPSS version 22. The study found that 84.6 percent of Temporary Agriculture Teachers in Homa-Bay County were satisfied with their jobs.

Keywords: Board of Management, Dissatisfiers, Homa-Bay County, Job Satisfaction, Motivators, Public Secondary School, Temporary Agriculture Teacher.

1. INTRODUCTION

Studies on job satisfaction from various occupations continue to emerge. When employees are satisfied, generally they care more about their work, are more committed, have higher retention rates, and are more productive [4] Studies have examined the levels, determinants and factors associated with levels of job satisfaction from every vocation ranging from nursing to sales, but more commonly in careers where high rates of attrition are common. These studies have all attempted to identify the factors associated with job satisfaction [6] Employees who are satisfied tend to care more about their work, are more committed to the organization, have higher retention rates, and tend to be more committed to the organization [4]. [1] further argues that job satisfaction is a complex phenomenon attributed to every vocation on earth.

Within the field of agricultural education, demands both in and out of the classroom have led many to question the level of job satisfaction among agricultural education teachers as a way to address issues facing the profession [5]. This seem to be in concurrence with the view of [27] that the main importance of job satisfaction includes the human values that are important in orienting the organization by respecting and treating their staff, the behaviour of employees as it impacts on the organization and assessment of employees and identification of the areas in need of improvement.

Job satisfaction is considered a key factor in improving shortage of teachers, according to education policy makers in North Carolina in the United States of America [6]. In Ghana, primary school teachers' motivation has declined as reported by [2]. This situation is similar to that of Nigeria as reported by [24] when he pointed out that teachers in Nigeria feel that they are cheated, underpaid and made to work in insecure environment where the government pays less attention to their dignity and self-esteem. Job satisfaction is therefore a universal phenomenon. Most of the expectations of workers, somewhat

correlate worldwide although there are divergent views arising from sociological, political and cultural backgrounds. However, there are similar expected aspects from a job from all global workers such as good pay, good environment, recognition and respecting their human rights.

In Kenya, staffing policies have evolved from the time the first school was set up by the missionaries and has changed from time to time during the colonial and post-colonial era. By independence (1963) recruitment of teachers had been supply driven. This was basically to replace the expatriates that were leaving and to cater for increased student enrolment. Under this system, graduates were posted as soon as they graduated from colleges. According to [17] the Government of Kenya (GoK) froze employment in the public sector, including teaching, in 1998. In 2001 this freeze was partially lifted and the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) was allowed to employ teachers to replace those exiting the service through natural attrition. The Teachers Service Commission then introduced a demand-driven policy on teacher recruitment. The shortage of teachers was never addressed and this situation worsened [19]. The situation has been exacerbated by the introduction of Free Primary Education (FPE) in 2003 and Free Day Secondary Education (FDSE) in 2008 by the Kenyan government. To meet the shortfall most schools employed teachers paid by boards of management [17]. However, there has not been any attempt to harmonize their terms of service by different schools and yet they have a direct impact on the learners' activities [21].

Studies by [20] in Kenya on job satisfaction among the teaching force majorly focussed on those employed by the TSC and revealed an increasing trend of job dissatisfaction among teachers. More particularly, the study by [25] pointed out that Rachuonyo South Sub-County which is an integral component of the county had qualified teachers that were expected to perform their tasks well yet this remained a tall order due to the motivation gaps that existed among schools within the Sub-County. This situation is similar to that of Mbita and Suba Sub-counties where there is a high teacher transfer requests indicating a high level of teacher transfer intention.

Although job satisfaction among the teaching force has been studied in Homa-Bay County, there still exists inconclusive literature about the job satisfaction of the temporary agriculture teachers in the County despite the fact that due to the ever persistent teacher shortage, BOM teaching force remains a permanent feature in Kenyan education sector. Teachers' Service Commission Act (1967) and the Education Act (1980) give mandate to the BOM of various schools to recruit qualified teachers to address the teacher shortage in schools. The BOM terms of employment tend to vary among schools [21] hence varied work conditions. This has led to little knowledge of the job dissatisfiers and motivators that influence the job satisfaction of Temporary Teachers especially those teaching agriculture as they perform extra duties such as farm management, conducting lab practical lessons and also offering extension service to the neighbouring community besides their normal classroom instruction.

This uniqueness of expectations from the agriculture teacher is not only particular to the Kenyan situation but also seems to be the case in North Carolina where [28] points out that, the pressures of family life and the duties and expectations of an agricultural teacher can place strain and stress on the teacher, which relates directly to their overall job satisfaction levels. The duties of the agricultural teacher go beyond the walls of the classroom and the closing bell of school to career development events, practices, field trips, and Supervised Agricultural Experience (SAE) visits to students' homes or employment. These additional duties add hours to the job and the work week and can make it difficult to fulfil family obligations [28]. It is important for the learners to be properly equipped with knowledge and skills in agriculture to enable them contribute significantly to the agriculture sector. Contributions of agriculture to the Kenyan economic development cannot be overlooked and they include provision of food, provision of raw materials to the agro based industries, provision of direct and indirect employment, provision of market for industrial goods, and exports of agriculture commodities earn the country foreign exchange.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Frederick Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory by [8] who argued that there are two sets of factors which either lead to job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. They are Motivating factors or satisfiers and Hygiene factors or dissatisfiers. Dissatisfiers are those factors related to the context of the job while satisfiers on the other hand included aspects related to the content of the job. According to Herzberg, managers who sought to eliminate job dissatisfiers could bring about workplace harmony but not necessarily motivation. Because they do not motivate employees, when these factors are adequate, people will not be dissatisfied; but at the same time they may not be fully satisfied. They will be in neutral state. If we want to motivate people on their jobs, it is suggested to give much importance on those job content factors which he called motivators.

The theory has a clear message for BOM in trying to motivate employees; the first step should be to eliminate dissatisfaction by ensuring that working conditions, interpersonal relations, appraisal, induction and supervision are reasonable. But these improvements will not lead to motivation, so the next step would be for BOM to enhance motivation by improving factors that cause satisfaction by ensuring that there are incentives, recognition, advancement, feedback provision and consultation [13]. Herzberg model sensitizes that merely treating the temporary agriculture teachers well through the good school policies is not sufficient to motivate them. Principals should utilize the skills, abilities, and talents of the temporary agriculture teachers at work through effective job designing. In other words, the work given to these teachers should be challenging and exciting and offer them a sense of achievement, recognition, and growth. Unless these characteristics are present in the job, these teachers would barely be satisfied with their job.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction

This chapter provides a description of how the study was conducted. It includes the research design, target population, sample size and sampling procedures, research instruments that were used, their validity and reliability, data collection procedures and data analysis techniques that will be used.

B. Research Design

The study made use of descriptive survey design. According to [12] the main purpose of descriptive design is to describe the state of affairs as it exists at present. Survey design was appropriate for this study since it was based on the assumption that the sample shares similar characteristics with the whole population from where it was drawn [26]. This design was chosen because the study does not require of the researcher to wait for a behaviour or response to occur in order to obtain data and is conducted simply to obtain a description of a particular group of individuals [12] such as Temporary Agriculture Teachers in a school.

C. Location of the Study

The study was carried out in Homa-Bay County which is situated in the Western region of Kenya in the former Nyanza Province. It is located in the Southern part of Lake Victoria. The county has a population of 963794 spread across its eight sub-counties. An ideal locale for a study should be easily accessible to the researcher and directly related to the researcher's interest. Homa-Bay County had a teacher shortage of 2182 secondary school teachers by 2016 with 137 exiting service the same year ranking it fourth in Kenya after Makueni, Bungoma and Kisii counties in terms of attrition [19]. By 2018 the shortage increased to 2395 of which agriculture and Kiswahili subjects were the most hit as reported by [22]. This has necessitated hiring of T temporary agriculture teachers in the County.

D. Target Population

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) a target population is that population to which the researcher wants to generalize the results of the study. The accessible population of this study was composed of approximately 316 Temporary agriculture teachers who were in service during data collection process. Majority of these teachers were found in the Sub-County and County Schools which formed 96 percent of the total number public secondary schools in the county. The staffing levels in these schools had been reported to be extremely inadequate (Homa-bay County Quality Assurance and Standards Report, 2012). These schools are geographically spread in the entire County reflecting different characteristics on the basis of, boarding boys' schools, boarding girls' schools, boarding mixed schools and mixed day schools. This indicated varied working conditions hence the need to establish the job satisfaction levels of these teachers.

E. Sampling Procedure and Sample size

[15] argues that the acceptable rule in determining sample size is to have a large sample as much as possible. There were about 316 Temporary Agriculture Teachers in the County. According to [14] with accessible population of 316 a sample of 176 Temporary Agriculture Teachers was adequate. [10] recommend a minimum sample of 100 respondents therefore a sample of 176 was chosen indicating 76 percent additional proportion to take care of attrition. Proportionate stratified random sampling was used in this study to get the number of Temporary Agriculture Teachers in each school category. A formula by [10] was used to obtain the number of members from each stratum (school category) which was arrived at as follows;

Table 1: Sample of Temporary Agriculture Teachers by school categories.

School category	Number of schools	Total Temporary Agriculture Teachers	Sample size
National	2	2	1
Extra-county	14	14	8
County	22	22	13
Sub-county	278	278	154
Total	316	316	176

Data source: County Education Magazine [9]

Purposive sampling was then used to select the 176 Temporary Agriculture Teachers.

F. Instrumentation

A researcher constructed questionnaire with close ended items using a Likert scale, divided into section A, B, C and D was used to acquire relevant information from the 176 Temporary Agriculture Teachers sampled. Section A sought the demographic information of the respondents while section B sought information on level of job satisfaction of Temporary Agriculture Teachers. Section C and D however focused on motivators and dissatisfiers respectively. Using a questionnaire ensured respondents remained anonymous and also gave them more time to think about the questions. A focus group discussion guide was also used by the researcher to probe some of the respondents further.

1) Validity

[15] define validity as the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which are on the research results. To achieve validity, the researcher gave the instrument to two agriculture teachers from the technical department of Obera secondary school as well as two experts from the Department of Agricultural Education and Extension in the Faculty of Education and Community Studies of Egerton University. They went through to check the content, face and construct validities, in reference to the study objectives so that each of the specific objectives would be captured in the questionnaire. Improvements were done accordingly.

2) Reliability

A reliable data collection instrument is one that yields dependable results [15]. To test the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was done among BOM Agriculture Teachers in public secondary schools in Migori County. [15] recommend that at least 10 percent of the sample size be used in testing for reliability of a research instrument. Consequently 29 Temporary Agriculture Teacher.were involved. The County was selected for pilot study because its schools had similar characteristics with the public secondary schools in Homa-bay County. After piloting, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was computed to determine reliability of the instrument. A coefficient of 0.70 or more implies that there is high degree of reliability. The same threshold was adopted in this study. A reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained. This was within the threshold for reliability testing and therefore the instrument was found to be consistent and reliable.

G. Data Collection Procedure

The researcher obtained an introductory letter from Board of Postgraduate Studies and research permit from National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) (Appendix C & D) to conduct research in the study location. The researcher then liaised with the County Education office and the County Commissioner's offices in the area to arrange for data collection. The researcher then visited the sampled schools and requested the respective principals for access to the respondents. The researcher then explained the purpose and the content of the questionnaire to the respondents before allowing them to fill. The respondents were then given twenty minutes to fill-in the questionnaires. Those that were not able to fill in the questionnaire in time were allowed one month to mail back the questionnaire to the researcher upon completion. A total of 176 questionnaires were administered. However, a total of 156 questionnaires were successfully filled and returned giving a return rate of 88.6 percent. Consequently, 20 (11.4%) questionnaires were not returned due to attrition.

H. Data Analysis

The collected data was first cleaned up for any errors such as incompleteness or inaccurate marking of responses. Data was then coded and recorded to reduce mass for ease of analysis. Data was then entered into the computer for analysis using

Statistical Packages for Social Sciences Version 22. Data on the dependent variable was summarized as Satisfaction of the Temporary Agriculture Teacher with the job under the following categories of Completely Satisfied (CS) = 6, Very satisfied (VS)=5, Fairly Satisfied (FS) = 4, Neither, Fairly Dissatisfied (FD) =3, Very Dissatisfied (VD)=2, and Completely dissatisfied (CD)= 1. 1= **Highest dissatisfaction** and 7= **Highest satisfaction**. Data on job satisfaction of Temporary Agriculture Teacher was measured as an index generated from respondent’s rating of 7 statements, each with a maximum of 6. The maximum score would be 42 if the respondent is completely satisfied with the seven statements implying the higher the score the higher the satisfaction. Consequently, the minimum score would be 6. This data was analyzed by percentages and mean scores. The following table indicates a summary of data analysis techniques that was adopted for the research question and hypotheses.

Information on Level of Job Satisfaction

This study was guided by the following question: What is the level of job satisfaction of temporary agriculture teachers in public secondary schools in Homa-Bay County? This information was important because it provided the impetus on the level of job satisfaction the respondents had. Study by [23] revealed that most school managers in Homa-bay County were not aware of job satisfaction levels of the teachers they manage. [7], asserts that job satisfaction and work motivation are synonymous as they are both based on employees needs and subsequent performance by the need seekers. In the study the respondents were asked to indicate how satisfied they were with their job. The results show that 84.6% of the respondents acknowledged to having been satisfied with their job with 13.5% being dissatisfied while 1.9% were not sure. As shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Level of Job Satisfaction of the Temporary Agriculture Teachers (n=156)

Options	Frequency	Percent
Dissatisfied	24	15.4
Satisfied	132	84.6
Total	156	100

The study revealed that the TATs were satisfied with the job to a large extent. This is so because 84.6 percent of the respondents indicated so. This finding contradicts that of [23] where he reported extremely low level of job satisfaction of teachers from Homa-bay County. Because TATs are satisfied with the job, dissatisfiers and motivator factors in place could have been effectively implemented. The implication of this is that majority Temporary Agriculture Teachers are satisfied with their job. The significance of this information is that there could be sets of dissatisfiers and motivators that are in place that contribute to job satisfaction of these teachers.

On a five point Likert scale, the respondents reflected their opinion concerning the level of agreement or disagreement with the statement. The responses are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Temporary Agriculture Teachers’ Job Satisfaction (n=156)

Question	Option				Total	
	Disagree		Agree		f	%
	F	%	f	%		
Apply for non-teaching jobs due to dissatisfaction	104	66.7	52	33.3	156	100
Don’t take up other duties in school because I am dissatisfied	114	73.1	42	26.9	156	100
Don’t Volunteer for extracurricular activities because I am dissatisfied	127	81.4	29	18.6	156	100
I do not Promote my school because I am dissatisfied	134	85.9	22	14.1	156	100
Come late to school because I am dissatisfied	117	75	39	25	156	100
Do not prepare professional documents because I am dissatisfied	122	78.2	34	21.8	156	100
I absent myself from school because I am dissatisfied	117	75	39	25	156	100
Averages	119	76.5	37	23.5	156	100

The respondents were asked to give their opinion on the view that they apply for other non-teaching jobs as a result of dissatisfaction with the current job as TAT. From the data, it can be shown that 66.7 percent of the respondents were in disagreement with the opinion while 33.3 percent agreed. A satisfied teacher is less likely to show interest in jobs outside the teaching profession. High attrition rate for teachers could indicate dissatisfaction with the job. These high percentages of TAT who do not apply for other non-teaching jobs could imply that majority of these teachers are satisfied with the job.

The respondents were asked to give their opinion on whether they fail to take up other responsibilities in school due to their dissatisfaction with the job. From these results, majority (73.1%) disagreed with the opinion while only (26.9%) were in agreement with the statement. A satisfied teacher is more likely to show active engagement in other responsibilities such as heading the agriculture department, educating farmers from the school community and being patron to Young Farmers Club. Failure to take up other responsibility would indicate dissatisfaction with the job. From the result, more than half of the TATs were willing to take up other responsibilities within the school and this could imply they are satisfied with the job.

The respondents were asked whether they fail to volunteer for extracurricular activities due to their dissatisfaction with the job. From the results, majority (81.4%) disagreed while only (18.6%) agreed. Majority Temporary Agriculture Teachers (76.3%) are aged between 21-25 years. Being youthful they are more likely to volunteer and engage students in games activities, start a Young Farmers Club in the school, and offer extension services to the community. Failure to volunteer for extracurricular activities would indicate dissatisfaction with the job. Nearly all, (81.4%) volunteered and engaged learners in extracurricular activities and this could imply they are satisfied with the job. The respondents were asked to give their opinion on whether they do not promote their schools due to their dissatisfaction with the job. Majority (85.9%) disagreed. Only a small number (14.1%) agreed with the statement. A satisfied teacher would contribute to school value by talking good about the school to other colleagues, parents and the community. Such teachers have good knowledge of the mission and vision of the school and would clarify any misinformation he/ she may encounter about the school. The higher number of TATs (85.9%) that talk good about the school could imply that they are satisfied with their jobs.

The respondents were asked to give their opinion on whether they come late to school due to their dissatisfaction with the job. Majority (75%) disagreed with the opinion. Only a small number (25%) agreed. A satisfied teacher will be punctual in reporting to school in order to prepare and attend the lessons in time. From the result, the high number (75%) of TATs that report to duty in time could signify satisfaction with the job. The respondents were asked to give their opinion on whether they fail to prepare professional documents for teaching due to their dissatisfaction with the job. From the results, majority (78.2%) disagreed with the opinion. Only a small number (21.8%) agreed with the statement. A satisfied teacher would be ethical in his/her work by preparing teaching notes, schemes of work, lesson plans, and teaching aids and use them with or without supervision. The teachers would also issue, mark, return and revise assignments. Failure to update teaching notes, attending lessons without professional documents would indicate dissatisfaction with the job. The result implies that majority (78.2%) of these teachers teach as required and are therefore satisfied with the job.

The respondents were asked to give their opinion on whether they absent themselves from duty due to their dissatisfaction with the job. Absenteeism of TATs from duty could indicate dissatisfaction with the job. From the results, majority (75%) disagreed with the opinion while a smaller number (25%) agreed. Majority of these teachers therefore have regular attendance to duty and this could imply that they are satisfied with the job.

The temporary teaching service was dominated by young and recent graduates. As reported by [23] terms of service and academic qualifications always have a bearing on teachers' job satisfaction and hence academic achievement. In his interview with school principals from the County, he established that teachers who were not on permanent employment worked hard hoping they would be recommended for confirmation though their job satisfaction levels remained low. He further reiterated that age, gender and length of service were not important issues with regards to the teacher job satisfaction levels and achievement. His findings were in support of that of [16] who observed that teachers in permanent employment have a feeling of belonging to the organization than one who is not and so the teacher will be satisfied with the teaching profession.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that the temporary agriculture teachers in Homa-Bay County were satisfied with their job. Their satisfaction with the job was contributed to by favourable Work condition and recognition of their effort. The Board of Management of secondary schools are called upon to maintain the working conditions in secondary schools as essential determinant of Temporary Agriculture Teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools, the temporary agriculture

teachers should be provided with agriculture technician for practical lessons, school farm, and life lab. Finally, the Board of Management and relevant authorities should ensure that the Temporary Agriculture Teachers' positive efforts are hailed, certificates are given to them on achievement as well as gifts as this motivates them and hence improves their job satisfaction which in turn improves their performance.

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